

Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4

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Abstract

*During past years author worked with **block-wise**, **bordered** and **block-bordered** magic squares. This work make connection between **block-wise** and **bordered** magic squares. We started with **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 108 and 104. Based on these two big magic inner order magic squares multiples of 4 are studied. By inner order we understand that magic squares of orders 100, 96, 92, etc. Instead of working in decreasing order, we worked with increasing orders, such as, orders 4, 8, 12, etc. The construction of the **block-wise bordered** magic squares multiples of 4 is based on equal sum blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The **block-wise bordered** magic squares studied are not **pandiagonal**. Redistributing the same blocks in each case, we get **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4, 8, 12, etc. This work is only for the multiples of order 4. The further multiples, such as multiples, 6, 8, 10, etc. shall be done in another works. [Examples are given only up to order 48. Higher orders examples can be seen in **Excel file** is attached with the work. The total work is up to order 108.](#)*

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1 Introduction

During past years author [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [15, 16, 17]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and p , where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [18, 19, 20, 21]. Some conection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are seperated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In many cases, we have to use fractional numbers entries, specially to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [1].

The aim of this work is to combine the study of **block-wise** and **bordered** magic squares. This kind of study still not seen by author. In this case we considers blocks of magic squares such as magic squares of order 4 and then put them in such a way that every time removing external borders, still we are left with magic squares. Based on this idea, we wrote with **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 108 and 104. Every time when we remove the external, we are left with **block-wise bordered** magic squares with minus order 8. For example, in case of order 108, removing external orders we are left with orders 100, 92, 84, etc. and in case of orders 104, removing external orders we are left with orders 96, 88, 80, etc. Thus alternatively we complete all order magic squares multiples of 4. The first two orders 4 and 8 are not **block-wise bordered** magic squares. From order 12 onwards, we always get **block-wise bordered** magic squares multiples of 4, i.e., of orders 12, 16, 20, etc. In all the situations the constructions of magic squares of order 4 are **pandiagonal** and of equal sums, while the **block-wise bordered** magic squares

are not **pandiagonal**. In each case, if we redistribute the blocks of order 4 already constructed we reach to **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 12, 16, 20, etc. but unfortunately they are no more **block-wise bordered** magic squares.

The main project is to write **block-wise bordered** magic squares as multiples of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, This idea of **block-wise bordered** magic squares is applied to **inlaid** magic square, where we can write different orders blocks in the same magic squares. For details refer author's recent work [22].

Initially, we have written the **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 108 and 104. In each case, the distribution entries are also given. The **pandiagonal** versions of these two magic squares are also given. Based on these two big **block-wise bordered** magic squares, we have given magic squares in increasing orders, i.e., of orders 4, 8, 12, . . . , 96, 100.

2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 108 and 104

2.1 Order 108

3 Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 8

3.1 Magic Square of Order 4

According to distribution (3), the entries for the magic square of order 4 are $D_{4 \times 4} := \{5825, \dots, 5840\}$. Subtracting 5824 from each value, we are left with entries $D_{4 \times 4} := \{1, \dots, 16\}$. These are the entries for magic square of order 4 starting from 1. This magic square is given below

7	12	1	14
2	13	8	11
16	3	10	5
9	6	15	4

It is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 34$.

3.2 Magic Squares of Order 8

According to distribution (6), the entries for the magic square of order 8 are $D_{8 \times 8} := \{5377, 5378, \dots, 5439, 5440\}$. Subtracting 5376 from each value, we are left with entries as $D_{8 \times 8} := \{1, \dots, 64\}$. These are the entries for the magic square of order 8 starting from 1. Below is this magic square of order 8.

7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54
2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51
64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13
57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12
31	36	25	38	23	44	17	46
26	37	32	35	18	45	24	43
40	27	34	29	48	19	42	21
33	30	39	28	41	22	47	20

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{8 \times 8} := 260$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 130$.

The above magic square is written according to blocks of order 4 appearing in Table-1044. For the entries $D_{8 \times 8} := \{1, \dots, 64\}$, this table is as given below:

1	2
4	3

The magic square of order 8 written according to above table is not a **pandiagonal**. In order to get a **pandiagonal**, let's change the order blocks 3 and 4 and write it as

1	2
3	4

According to above table the magic square of order 8 is given by

7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54
2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51
64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13
57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12
23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38
18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35
48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29
41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28

In this case, the above magic square of order 8 is **pandiagonal** with equal sum **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The magic sums are $S_{8 \times 8} := 260$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 130$.

4 Magic Square of Order 12

According to distribution (3), the entries for magic square of order 12 are given by

$$D_{12 \times 12} := \{5761, \dots, 5824, D_{4 \times 4}, 5841, \dots, 5904\}$$

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{5825, \dots, 5840\}$$

From Table 1, the magic square of order 12 stands as

721	722	723
728	729	724
727	726	725

Table-12a

(7)

Subtracting 5760 from each value of distribution (??), we get entries for the magic square of order 12 starting from 1. These entries are as follows

$$D_{12 \times 12} := \{1, \dots, 64, D_{4 \times 4}, 81, \dots, 144\}$$

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{65, \dots, 80\}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (??), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 12. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

4.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (??), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 12 is given by

1	2	3
8	9	4
7	6	5

Table-12b

(8)

The **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 12 is given by

7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126
2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123
144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21
137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20
63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	31	116	25	118
58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	26	117	32	115
88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	120	27	114	29
81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	113	30	119	28
55	92	49	94	47	100	41	102	39	108	33	110
50	93	56	91	42	101	48	99	34	109	40	107
96	51	90	53	104	43	98	45	112	35	106	37
89	54	95	52	97	46	103	44	105	38	111	36

The magic sums are $S_{12 \times 12} := 870$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 290$.

4.2 Pandiagonal

Let's rewrite the Table 8 as given below

1	2	3
4	5	6
7	8	9

Table-12c

(9)

According to Table 9, the magic square of order 12 is given by

Subtracting 5376 from each value given in (15), we are left with following distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{1, \dots, 128, D_{12 \times 12}, 273, \dots, 400\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{129, \dots, 192, D_{4 \times 4}, 209, \dots, 272\} \\
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{193, \dots, 208\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (17), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 20. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

6.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (17), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 20 is given by

1	2	3	4	5
16	17	18	19	6
15	24	25	20	7
14	23	22	21	8
13	12	11	10	9

Table-20b (18)

In this case the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 20 is given by

641	642	643	644	645	646
660	661	662	663	664	647
659	672	673	674	665	648
658	671	676	675	666	649
657	670	669	668	667	650
656	655	654	653	652	651

Table-24a

(21)

Subtracting 5120 from each value given in (20), we are left with following distribution:

$$D_{24 \times 24} := \{1, \dots, 160, D_{16 \times 16}, 417, \dots, 576\}$$

$$D_{16 \times 16} := \{161, \dots, 256, D_{8 \times 8}, 321, \dots, 416\}$$

$$D_{8 \times 8} := \{257, \dots, 288, 289, \dots, 320\}$$

(22)

Based on the entries given in distribution (22), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 24. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

7.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (22), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 24 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6
20	21	22	23	24	7
19	32	33	34	25	8
18	31	366	35	26	9
17	30	29	28	27	10
16	15	14	13	12	11

Table-24

(23)

In this case the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 24 is given by

681	682	683	684	685	686	687
704	705	706	707	708	709	688
703	720	721	722	723	710	689
702	719	728	729	724	711	690
701	718	727	726	725	712	691
700	717	716	715	714	713	692
699	698	697	696	695	694	693

Table-28a

(26)

Subtracting 5440 from each value given in (25), we are left with following distribution:

$$D_{28 \times 28} := \{1, \dots, 192, D_{20 \times 20}, 593, \dots, 784\}$$

$$D_{20 \times 20} := \{193, \dots, 320, D_{12 \times 12}, 465, \dots, 592\}$$

$$D_{12 \times 12} := \{321, \dots, 384, D_{4 \times 4}, 401, \dots, 464\}$$

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{385, \dots, 400\}$$

(27)

Based on the entries given in distribution (27), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 28. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

8.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (27), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 28 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24	25	26	27	28	29	8
23	40	41	42	43	30	9
22	39	48	49	44	31	10
21	38	47	46	45	32	11
20	37	36	35	34	33	12
19	18	17	16	15	14	13

Table-28

(28)

In this case the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 28 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	31	32	33	34	35
36	37	38	39	40	41	42
43	44	45	46	47	48	49

Table-28c

(29)

According to Table-28c(29), the magic square of order 28 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{4897, \dots, 5120, D_{24 \times 24}, 5697, \dots, 5920\}; \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{5121, \dots, 5280, D_{16 \times 16}, 5537, \dots, 5696\}; \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{5281, \dots, 5376, D_{8 \times 8}, 5441, \dots, 5536\}; \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{5377, 5378, \dots, 5439, 5440\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

In view of Table-1044, the magic square of order 32 for the entries given in distribution (30) is as follows:

613	614	615	616	617	618	619	620
640	641	642	643	644	645	646	621
639	660	661	662	663	664	647	622
638	659	672	673	674	665	648	623
637	658	671	676	675	666	649	624
636	657	670	669	668	667	650	625
635	656	655	654	653	652	651	626
634	633	632	631	630	629	628	627

Table-32a (31)

Subtracting 4896 from each value given in (30), we are left with following distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{1, \dots, 224, D_{24 \times 24}, 801, \dots, 1024\} \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{225, \dots, 384, D_{16 \times 16}, 641, \dots, 800\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{385, \dots, 480, D_{8 \times 8}, 545, \dots, 640\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{481, \dots, 512, 513, \dots, 544\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (32), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 32. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

9.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (32), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 32 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
28	29	30	31	32	33	34	9
27	48	49	50	51	52	35	10
26	47	60	61	62	53	36	11
25	46	59	64	63	54	37	12
24	45	58	57	56	55	38	13
23	44	43	42	41	40	39	14
22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15

Table-32

(33)

In this case the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 32 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40
41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56
57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64

Table-32c

(34)

According to Table-32c(34), the magic square of order 32 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{5185, \dots, 5440, D_{28 \times 28}, 6225, \dots, 6480\}; \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{5441, \dots, 5632, D_{20 \times 20}, 6033, \dots, 6224\}; \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{5633, \dots, 5760, D_{12 \times 12}, 5905, \dots, 6032\}; \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{5761, \dots, 5824, D_{4 \times 4}, 5841, \dots, 5904\}; \\
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{5825, \dots, 5840\}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{35}$$

In view of Table-1081, the magic square of order 36 for the entries given in distribution (35) is as follows:

649	650	651	652	653	654	655	656	657
680	681	682	683	684	685	686	687	658
679	704	705	706	707	708	709	688	659
678	703	720	721	722	723	710	689	660
677	702	719	728	729	724	711	690	661
676	701	718	727	726	725	712	691	662
675	700	717	716	715	714	713	692	663
674	699	698	697	696	695	694	693	664
673	672	671	670	669	668	667	666	665

Table-36a (36)

Subtracting 5184 from each value given in (35), we are left with following distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{1, \dots, 256, D_{28 \times 28}, 1041, \dots, 1296\} \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{257, \dots, 448, D_{20 \times 20}, 849, \dots, 1040\} \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{449, \dots, 576, D_{12 \times 12}, 721, \dots, 848\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{577, \dots, 640, D_{4 \times 4}, 657, \dots, 720\} \quad D_{4 \times 4} := \{641, \dots, 656\}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{37}$$

Based on the entries given in (37), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 36 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	10
31	56	57	58	59	60	61	40	11
30	55	72	73	74	75	62	41	12
29	54	71	80	81	76	63	42	13
28	53	70	79	78	77	64	43	14
27	52	69	68	67	66	65	44	15
26	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	16
25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45
46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54
55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63
64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72
73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81

Table-36c

(39)

According to Table-36c(39), the magic square of order 36 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	11
35	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	45	12
34	63	84	85	86	87	88	71	46	13
33	62	83	96	97	98	89	72	47	14
32	61	82	95	100	99	90	73	48	15
31	60	81	94	93	92	91	74	49	16
30	59	80	79	78	77	76	75	50	17
29	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	18
28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	20	19

Table-40

(43)

In this case the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 40 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40
41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50
51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60
61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70
71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80
81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90
91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100

Table-40c

(44)

According to Table-40c(44), the magic square of order 40 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{44 \times 44} &:= \{4865, \dots, 5184, D_{36 \times 36}, 6481, \dots, 6800\}; \\
 D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{5185, \dots, 5440, D_{28 \times 28}, 6225, \dots, 6480\}; \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{5441, \dots, 5632, D_{20 \times 20}, 6033, \dots, 6224\}; \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{5633, \dots, 5760, D_{12 \times 12}, 5905, \dots, 6032\}; \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{5761, \dots, 5824, D_{4 \times 4}, 5841, \dots, 5904\}; \\
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{5825, \dots, 5840\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

In view of Table-1081, the magic square of order 44 for the entries given in distribution (45) is as follows:

609	610	611	612	613	614	615	616	617	618	619
648	649	650	651	652	653	654	655	656	657	620
647	680	681	682	683	684	685	686	687	658	621
646	679	704	705	706	707	708	709	688	659	622
645	678	703	720	721	722	723	710	689	660	623
644	677	702	719	728	729	724	711	690	661	624
643	676	701	718	727	726	725	712	691	662	625
642	675	700	717	716	715	714	713	692	663	626
641	674	699	698	697	696	695	694	693	664	627
640	673	672	671	670	669	668	667	666	665	628
639	638	637	636	635	634	633	632	631	630	629

Table-44a (46)

Subtracting 4864 from each value given in (45), we are left with following distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{44 \times 44} &:= \{1, \dots, 320, D_{36 \times 36}, 1617, \dots, 1936\} \\
 D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{321, \dots, 576, D_{28 \times 28}, 1361, \dots, 1616\} \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{577, \dots, 768, D_{20 \times 20}, 1169, \dots, 1360\} \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{769, \dots, 896, D_{12 \times 12}, 1041, \dots, 1168\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{897, \dots, 960, D_{4 \times 4}, 977, \dots, 1040\} \\
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{961, \dots, 976\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (47), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 44. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

12.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (47), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 44 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	12
39	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	50	13
38	71	96	97	98	99	100	101	80	51	14
37	70	95	112	113	114	115	102	81	52	15
36	69	94	111	120	121	116	103	82	53	16
35	68	93	110	119	118	117	104	83	54	17
34	67	92	109	108	107	106	105	84	55	18
33	66	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	56	19
32	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	20
31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21

Table-44b

(48)

In this case the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 44 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44
45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55
56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66
67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77
78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88
89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99
100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110
111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121

Table-44c

(49)

According to Table-44c(49), the magic square of order 44 is given by

13.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (52), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 48 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	13
43	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	55	14
42	79	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	89	56	15
41	78	107	128	129	130	131	132	115	90	57	16
40	77	106	127	140	141	142	133	116	91	58	17
39	76	105	126	139	144	143	134	117	92	59	18
38	75	104	125	138	137	136	135	118	93	60	19
37	74	103	124	123	122	121	120	119	94	61	20
36	73	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	62	21
35	72	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	22
34	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23

Table-48b

(53)

In this case the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 48 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60
61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72
73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84
85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96
97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120
121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132
133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144

Table-48c

(54)

According to Table-48c(54), the magic square of order 48 is given by

bordered and another is **pandiagonal**.

14.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (57), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 52 is given by

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	14
47	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	60	15
46	87	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	98	61	16
45	86	119	144	145	146	147	148	149	128	99	62	17
44	85	118	143	160	161	162	163	150	129	100	63	18
43	84	117	142	159	168	169	164	151	130	101	64	19
42	83	116	141	158	167	166	165	152	131	102	65	20
41	82	115	140	157	156	155	154	153	132	103	66	21
40	81	114	139	138	137	136	135	134	133	104	67	22
39	80	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	68	23
38	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	70	69	24
37	36	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	26	25

Table-52b

(58)

In this case the magic sums are $S_{52 \times 52} := 70330$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 5410$.

14.2 Pandiagonal

Let's rewrite the Table 58 as given below

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52
53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65
66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78
79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91
92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104
105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117
118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130
131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143
144	145	146	147	148	149	150	151	152	153	154	155	156
157	158	159	160	161	162	163	164	165	166	167	168	169

Table-52c

(59)

The above magic square constructed according to above table is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 52 with equal sums blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The magic sums are $S_{52 \times 52} := 70330$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 5410$.

15 Magic Square of Order 56

According to distribution (6), the entries for magic square of order 56 are

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{56 \times 56} &:= \{3841, \dots, 4256, D_{48 \times 48}, 6561, \dots, 6976\}; \\
 D_{48 \times 48} &:= \{4257, \dots, 4608, D_{40 \times 40}, 6209, \dots, 6560\}; \\
 D_{40 \times 40} &:= \{4609, \dots, 4896, D_{32 \times 32}, 5921, \dots, 6208\}; \\
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{4897, \dots, 5120, D_{24 \times 24}, 5697, \dots, 5920\}; \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{5121, \dots, 5280, D_{16 \times 16}, 5537, \dots, 5696\}; \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{5281, \dots, 5376, D_{8 \times 8}, 5441, \dots, 5536\}; \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{5377, 5378, \dots, 5439, 5440\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

(60)

In view of Table-1044, the magic square of order 56 for the entries given in distribution (60) is as follows:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	17
59	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	75	18
58	111	156	157	158	159	160	161	162	163	164	165	166	125	76	19
57	110	155	192	193	194	195	196	197	198	199	200	167	126	77	20
56	109	154	191	220	221	222	223	224	225	226	201	168	127	78	21
55	108	153	190	219	240	241	242	243	244	227	202	169	128	79	22
54	107	152	189	218	239	252	253	254	245	228	203	170	129	80	23
53	106	151	188	217	238	251	256	255	246	229	204	171	130	81	24
52	105	150	187	216	237	250	249	248	247	230	205	172	131	82	25
51	104	149	186	215	236	235	234	233	232	231	206	173	132	83	26
50	103	148	185	214	213	212	211	210	209	208	207	174	133	84	27
49	102	147	184	183	182	181	180	179	178	177	176	175	134	85	28
48	101	146	145	144	143	142	141	140	139	138	137	136	135	86	29
47	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	30
46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	31

Table-64b

(73)

In this case the magic sums are $S_{64 \times 64} := 131104$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 8194$.

17.2 Pandiagonal

Let's rewrite the Table 73 as given below

$$\begin{aligned} D_{80 \times 80} &:= \{1, \dots, 608, D_{72 \times 72}, 5793, \dots, 6400\} \\ D_{72 \times 72} &:= \{609, \dots, 1152, D_{64 \times 64}, 5249, \dots, 5792\} \\ D_{64 \times 64} &:= \{1153, \dots, 1632, D_{56 \times 56}, 4769, \dots, 5248\} \\ D_{56 \times 56} &:= \{1633, \dots, 2048, D_{48 \times 48}, 4353, \dots, 4768\} \\ D_{48 \times 48} &:= \{2049, \dots, 2400, D_{40 \times 40}, 4001, \dots, 4352\} \\ D_{40 \times 40} &:= \{2401, \dots, 2688, D_{32 \times 32}, 3713, \dots, 4000\} \\ D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{2689, \dots, 2912, D_{24 \times 24}, 3489, \dots, 3712\} \\ D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{2913, \dots, 3072, D_{16 \times 16}, 3329, \dots, 3488\} \\ D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{3073, \dots, 3168, D_{8 \times 8}, 3233, \dots, 3328\} \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{3169, \dots, 3200, 3201, \dots, 3232\}. \end{aligned} \tag{92}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (92), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 80. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

21.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (92), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 80 is given by

Subtracting 2304 from each value given in (95), we are left with following distribution:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{84 \times 84} &:= \{1, \dots, 640, D_{76 \times 76}, 6417, \dots, 7056\} \\ D_{76 \times 76} &:= \{641, \dots, 1216, D_{68 \times 68}, 5841, \dots, 6416\} \\ D_{68 \times 68} &:= \{1217, \dots, 1728, D_{60 \times 60}, 5329, \dots, 5840\} \\ D_{60 \times 60} &:= \{1729, \dots, 2176, D_{52 \times 52}, 4881, \dots, 5328\} \\ D_{52 \times 52} &:= \{2177, \dots, 2560, D_{44 \times 44}, 4497, \dots, 4880\} \\ D_{44 \times 44} &:= \{2561, \dots, 2880, D_{36 \times 36}, 4177, \dots, 4496\} \\ D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{2881, \dots, 3136, D_{28 \times 28}, 3921, \dots, 4176\} \\ D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{3137, \dots, 3328, D_{20 \times 20}, 3729, \dots, 3920\} \\ D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{3329, \dots, 3456, D_{12 \times 12}, 3601, \dots, 3728\} \\ D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{3457, \dots, 3520, D_{4 \times 4}, 3537, \dots, 3600\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{3521, \dots, 3536\}. \end{aligned} \tag{97}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (97), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 84. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

22.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (97), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 84 is given by

Table-88a

(101)

Subtracting 1536 from each value given in (100), we entries for magic square of order 88 starting from 1:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{88 \times 88} &:= \{1, \dots, 672, D_{80 \times 80}, 7073, 7744\} \\
 D_{80 \times 80} &:= \{673, \dots, 1280, D_{72 \times 72}, 6465, \dots, 7072\} \\
 D_{72 \times 72} &:= \{1281, \dots, 1824, D_{64 \times 64}, 5921, \dots, 6464\} \\
 D_{64 \times 64} &:= \{1825, \dots, 2304, D_{56 \times 56}, 5441, \dots, 5920\} \\
 D_{56 \times 56} &:= \{2305, \dots, 2720, D_{48 \times 48}, 5025, \dots, 5440\} \\
 D_{48 \times 48} &:= \{2721, \dots, 3072, D_{40 \times 40}, 4673, \dots, 5024\} \\
 D_{40 \times 40} &:= \{3073, \dots, 3360, D_{32 \times 32}, 4385, \dots, 4672\} \\
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{3361, \dots, 3584, D_{24 \times 24}, 4161, \dots, 4384\} \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{3585, \dots, 3744, D_{16 \times 16}, 4001, \dots, 4160\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{3745, \dots, 3840, D_{8 \times 8}, 3905, \dots, 4000\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{3841, \dots, 3872, 3873, \dots, 3904\}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{102}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (102), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 88. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

23.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (102), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 88 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} D_{92 \times 92} &:= \{1601, \dots, 2304, D_{84 \times 84}, 9361, \dots, 10064\}; \\ D_{84 \times 84} &:= \{2305, \dots, 2944, D_{76 \times 76}, 8721, \dots, 9360\}; \\ D_{76 \times 76} &:= \{2945, \dots, 3520, D_{68 \times 68}, 8145, \dots, 8720\}; \\ D_{68 \times 68} &:= \{3521, \dots, 4032, D_{60 \times 60}, 7633, \dots, 8144\}; \\ D_{60 \times 60} &:= \{4033, \dots, 4480, D_{52 \times 52}, 7185, \dots, 7632\}; \\ D_{52 \times 52} &:= \{4481, \dots, 4864, D_{44 \times 44}, 6801, \dots, 7184\}; \\ D_{44 \times 44} &:= \{4865, \dots, 5184, D_{36 \times 36}, 6481, \dots, 6800\}; \\ D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{5185, \dots, 5440, D_{28 \times 28}, 6225, \dots, 6480\}; \\ D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{5441, \dots, 5632, D_{20 \times 20}, 6033, \dots, 6224\}; \\ D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{5633, \dots, 5760, D_{12 \times 12}, 5905, \dots, 6032\}; \\ D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{5761, \dots, 5824, D_{4 \times 4}, 5841, \dots, 5904\}; \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{5825, \dots, 5840\}. \end{aligned} \tag{105}$$

In view of Table-1081, the magic square of order 92 for the entries given in distribution (105) is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{92 \times 92} &:= \{1, \dots, 704, D_{84 \times 84}, 7761, \dots, 8464\} \\
 D_{84 \times 84} &:= \{705, \dots, 1344, D_{76 \times 76}, 7121, \dots, 7760\} \\
 D_{76 \times 76} &:= \{1345, \dots, 1920, D_{68 \times 68}, 6545, \dots, 7120\} \\
 D_{68 \times 68} &:= \{1921, \dots, 2432, D_{60 \times 60}, 6033, \dots, 6544\} \\
 D_{60 \times 60} &:= \{2433, \dots, 2880, D_{52 \times 52}, 5585, \dots, 6032\} \\
 D_{52 \times 52} &:= \{2881, \dots, 3264, D_{44 \times 44}, 5201, \dots, 5584\} \\
 D_{44 \times 44} &:= \{3265, \dots, 3584, D_{36 \times 36}, 4881, \dots, 5200\} \\
 D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{3585, \dots, 3840, D_{28 \times 28}, 4625, \dots, 4880\} \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{3841, \dots, 4032, D_{20 \times 20}, 4433, \dots, 4624\} \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{4033, \dots, 4160, D_{12 \times 12}, 4305, \dots, 4432\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{4161, \dots, 4224, D_{4 \times 4}, 4241, \dots, 4304\} \\
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{4225, \dots, 4240\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{107}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (107), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 92. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

24.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (107), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 92 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} D_{96 \times 96} &:= \{801, \dots, 1536, D_{88 \times 88}, 9281, \dots, 10016\}; \\ D_{88 \times 88} &:= \{1537, \dots, 2208, D_{80 \times 80}, 8609, \dots, 9280\}; \\ D_{80 \times 80} &:= \{2209, \dots, 2816, D_{72 \times 72}, 8001, \dots, 8608\}; \\ D_{72 \times 72} &:= \{2817, \dots, 3360, D_{64 \times 64}, 7457, \dots, 8000\}; \\ D_{64 \times 64} &:= \{3361, \dots, 3840, D_{56 \times 56}, 6977, \dots, 7456\}; \\ D_{56 \times 56} &:= \{3841, \dots, 4256, D_{48 \times 48}, 6561, \dots, 6976\}; \\ D_{48 \times 48} &:= \{4257, \dots, 4608, D_{40 \times 40}, 6209, \dots, 6560\}; \\ D_{40 \times 40} &:= \{4609, \dots, 4896, D_{32 \times 32}, 5921, \dots, 6208\}; \\ D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{4897, \dots, 5120, D_{24 \times 24}, 5697, \dots, 5920\}; \\ D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{5121, \dots, 5280, D_{16 \times 16}, 5537, \dots, 5696\}; \\ D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{5281, \dots, 5376, D_{8 \times 8}, 5441, \dots, 5536\}; \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{5377, 5378, \dots, 5439, 5440\}. \end{aligned} \tag{110}$$

In view of Table-1044, the magic square of order 96 for the entries given in distribution (110) is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{96 \times 96} &:= \{1, \dots, 736, D_{88 \times 88}, 8481, \dots, 9216\} \\
 D_{88 \times 88} &:= \{737, \dots, 1408, D_{80 \times 80}, 7809, \dots, 8480\} \\
 D_{80 \times 80} &:= \{1409, \dots, 2016, D_{72 \times 72}, 7201, \dots, 7808\} \\
 D_{72 \times 72} &:= \{2017, \dots, 2560, D_{64 \times 64}, 6657, \dots, 7200\} \\
 D_{64 \times 64} &:= \{2561, \dots, 3040, D_{56 \times 56}, 6177, \dots, 6656\} \\
 D_{56 \times 56} &:= \{3041, \dots, 3456, D_{48 \times 48}, 5761, \dots, 6176\} \\
 D_{48 \times 48} &:= \{3457, \dots, 3808, D_{40 \times 40}, 5409, \dots, 5760\} \\
 D_{40 \times 40} &:= \{3809, \dots, 4096, D_{32 \times 32}, 5121, \dots, 5408\} \\
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{4097, \dots, 4320, D_{24 \times 24}, 4897, \dots, 5120\} \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{4321, \dots, 4480, D_{16 \times 16}, 4737, \dots, 4896\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{4481, \dots, 4576, D_{8 \times 8}, 4641, \dots, 4736\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{4577, \dots, 4608, 4609, \dots, 4640\}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{112}$$

Based on the entries given in distribution (112), below are two different kinds of magic squares of order 96. One is **block-wise bordered** and another is **pandiagonal**.

25.1 Block-Wise Bordered

According to entries given in distribution (112), the new table for the **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 96 is given by

